

Pioneering AI in MLTC: Bridging Research and Practice

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The
Alan Turing
Institute

Swansea
University
Prifysgol
Abertawe

Population Data Science
Gwyddor Data Poblogaeth

Focussing on the future:

How do we ensure impact through translation of your research to improve health & social care for MLTC patients, in the next 5 years?

The workshop logistics

The workshop was designed to provide members of the AIM community with an opportunity to discuss key topics shaping the future of AI and MLTC research, aiming to improve lives for those living with or caring for people with Multiple Long-Term Conditions. In collaboration with NIHR, six discussion topics with guiding questions were prepared to explore challenges and potential solutions.

The event welcomed 80-100 registered attendees, with 12-16 participants engaging in discussions on each topic and eight joining online. A one-hour session included 50 minutes for discussion, focusing on capturing attendees' insights and identifying three key takeaways for feedback.

There were 7 topics discussed in the workshop, this summary includes the discussion and takeaway from the 3rd topic.

- **Topic 1: How can we mobilise knowledge that has been generated by AIM?**
- **Topic 2: What are the strategies & good practices for engaging and sustaining patient communities?**
- **Topic 3: How can we champion early career researchers in MLTC research?**
- **Topic 4: What technical support is needed for the next stage of translation/impact?**
- **Topic 5: Who do we need to engage to ensure broad collaboration for translating research?**
- **Topic 6: How would we move towards system thinking and transdisciplinary research in MLTC?**
- **Topic 7: What are the strategies & good practices for engaging and sustaining patient communities?**

Topic 3: How can we champion early career researchers in MLTC research?

Chaired and Scribed by: Emma Karoune and Rafael Henkin

The key takeaways

1. Funding - Longer term funding of ECRs on MLTC research to retain knowledge and skills, lack of opportunity for smaller grants to learn how to manage projects and lead.
2. ECR Training needs - Mentorship/shadowing and onboarding - by PPIE reps, PIs, ECRs.
3. Senior Team/PI needs training in interdisciplinary and inclusive working - to enable ECRs - mentorship/shadowing for ECRs to become project leaders, running inclusive meetings.

Recommendations for MLTC funders

1. Create a sustainable ECR development framework:
 - Establish dedicated funding streams for ECR-led pilot projects
 - Build mentorship programmes with protected time for both mentors and mentees
 - Support shadowing opportunities across different MLTC projects
 - Develop training programmes in interdisciplinary & transdisciplinary research methods
 - Include ECR positions in longer-term funding packages
2. Establish an MLTC research career support programme:
 - Create an MLTC research guidebook for newcomers to the field
 - Fund regular ideas cafés and networking events
 - Develop formal training partnerships with PPIE representatives
 - Support ECR involvement in grant writing and project development
 - Create dedicated spaces for ECR voices in large project meetings
 - Build a network for sharing job opportunities across MLTC research

Summary of all the discussion

- ECR meetings - is doing this on a project/programme basis - how do we maintain funding for this?
 - Educate people/researchers of MLTC/polypharmacy - educating researchers as they are coming up/being trained.
 - PPIE training - at the university level

- PPIE groups to shape research - talking to students about what PPIE reps did.
 - ideas cafes uni of Exeter for PPIE - monthly-ish
- Be involved in the application process - writing the next projects with PIs
 - Educating management group
- Mentorship -
- Career planning - I never worked with healthcare research before, not sure what is next.
- To know about potential career paths - guidance.
- Jobs in the network - related to this type of research.
- Smaller grants/pilot projects for ECR in MLTC research
- No guidebook on MLTC
- Support for mentors/Pis - mentorship/training of mentors, collaborative and inclusive working practices.
- ECR voice can get lost in large meetings and groups, creating a space/awareness.
- Interdisciplinary - training and experience, shadowing/mentorship.
- Training - cross-project
- Sharing knowledge across projects would be useful – (how?)